

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS AND INFORMATICS

BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN THE GLOBAL EDUCATION SPACE

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Abstract

Informatization of education is considered as one of the most important strategic directions of civilization development. The problems that hinder the full participation of countries in the globalization of the world educational space, including the low level of use of big data technologies, are highlighted. The conclusion about the prospects of using blockchain technology, which allows creating shared educational services and resources, monitor the educational content and the quality of educational programs, to identify documents on education.

Keywords: world educational space, globalization, blockchain technology.

The digital transformation of education occurring in the 21st century is a practical embodiment of the concept of "Education 4.0. The concept is focused on the creation of such an educational system, which in its focus corresponds to the requirements of the "fourth industrial revolution", which is manifested in the mass implementation of cyber-physical systems in production (Industry 4.0). According to experts, without adapting informatization of education to the requirements of the "fourth industrial revolution", human civilization can expect even greater "information inequality" in society, deepening institutional problems associated with "information asymmetry" [5]. We consider informatization as a circulatory system of global trends in the international educational space. These global trends include: democratization of the education system; ensuring the right to education for all who wish; the influence of socio-economic factors on education; creation of a market for educational services and its requirements; expansion of the higher education network; searching for a compromise between rigid centralization and complete autonomy of education; constant updating and adjustment of school and university educational programs; a shift from orientation toward the "average" student: searching for additional resources for education with deviations in different.

Globalization of the world educational space is a phenomenon that reflects the globalization of all spheres of society (economy, politics, culture). All these spheres are penetrated by the meridians of information technology. The trends of global education space formation we refer to: the emergence of a global education market, the diffusion of pedagogical technologies; the emergence of educational transnational corporations, education informatization; convergence, involving the merger and interpenetration of educational and social systems; integration of educational systems; standardization, both educational systems and educational programs [4,7]

The global educational space is in the process of formation and is subject to the same laws of functioning as the global socio-economic space: that is, the organization of the educational process is centered on the principles of freedom of choice of types and forms of

educational activity, market competition, self-regulation and free pricing.

The objective conditions of the activity of the subjects of globalizing educational space demonstrate the circular relationship and the effect of the gap between the requirements for the quality of students' training and the actual capabilities of the educational system to meet these requirements. Thus, the level of digital transformation capability in different segments of the global education space, closely connected with the level of information asymmetry in different segments of the global education space determine the structure and quality of national markets of educational structures, and themselves depend on the world community's need for quality education, education quality standards and the ability of the education system to meet these standards. All this determines the structure and quality of the global market of educational services.

Understanding the structure and quality of the global educational space makes it possible to identify the conditions of its functioning, to analyze the changes occurring in it, given that the qualitative and quantitative changes occurring in the system of education occur with different intensity. We refer the effects of hysteresis, digital transformation, information asymmetry to the qualitative characteristics of the space, and to the conditionally quantitative ones - its ability to provide the labor market with specialists, as well as the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals. This approach forms the basis for revision of conditions for functioning and standardization of existing qualitative characteristics of the Global Education Space, standardization of criteria for comparison of cross-country big data to monitor the achievement of SDG 4, formation of a mechanism to ensure equal access of subjects of educational activity to all elements of the Global Education Space, standardization and control of conditions for such participation, ensuring security and joint use of data, and the use of data in a safe and secure way. Approaches to the solution of this problem objectively lead to the idea of the need to use blockchain technology in the development of modern education system [6].

The analysis of the scientific literature allowed us to formulate the possibilities of application of this technology for information support of the processes of globalization of the educational space. With regard to education, blockchain is considered, firstly, as a system of storage of specific information related to the educational sphere, using a software module that implements an algorithm that processes the information content of ordered, interconnected data blocks as a whole using cryptographic technologies and data protection technologies to ensure and maintain the integrity of the Global Education Space [3]. First, it controls the passage of transactions performed by an educational organization, which can be considered the minimum amount of information transactions that make sense and are considered fully completed (e.g., the issuance of a certificate of educational attainment). Second, blockchain technology provides: a high level of security for data storage and transmission, an open and transparent network infrastructure, decentralization and low operating costs. We have made a basic scheme for the use of blockchain technology in the field of education. The first link is the educational organization's need to send (receive) information that meets (must meet) the requirements of reliability, objectivity, completeness, etc. Transactions (information transfer) take place by placing information in the network, its receipt is carried out in the form of a reference to the placed information. The information arrives in a block, having its own number and hash of the previous block. Blocks are sent to all participants of the automated information exchange system for verification. If the information corresponds to the requirements, each participant of the information exchange includes the "block" in its database [1].

This block is included in the chain of blocks, which contains information about all previous transactions. Such information is delivered to the user, who a priori can consider this information to be reliable and compliant with the requirements that are formulated for this information. The conclusion is made about the promising use of blockchain technology, which gives the possibility to create common educational services and resources, to control educational content and the quality of educational programs, to identify documents on education. Blockchain technology is the ability to create a centralized public distributed network; the ability to create a centralized private (with a limited number of participants) distributed network; confidentiality (the ability to restrict access to some information); technology to ensure data integrity and consistency (consensus); high throughput / number of transactions per second; technology to create decentralized applications and smart contracts; technology to organize and synchronize data [2].

However, there are a number of problems that prevent the full participation of countries in the globalization of the world educational space, including the low level of use of big data technologies.

These are inactive marketing policy of Russian education, insufficient effectiveness of distance learning and online education, lagging behind the information

infrastructure of Russian universities, including the use of blockchain technology, lack of awareness of educational organizations and teachers about global trends in education development, the Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development, Sustainable Development Goal 4. The latter circumstance is associated with both low level of scientific interest and insufficient technological support of blockchain technology functioning.

The activity of different countries in blockchain technology development differs significantly. For example, if the number of patents in the blockchain technology among countries (as of April 2020) was 825 in China, 648 in the U.S., 16 in India, and 2 in Russia [4].

According to the modern globalization paradigm of the civilization process, while preserving the national characteristics of educational systems, they have common features and development trends, there is a "diffusion of pedagogical innovation," which accelerates the movement forward. Blockchain technology is an important tool that can optimize this process. The introduction of this technology contributes to the creation of a common educational space, cross-country comparison, collection and storage of statistical data on a large number of educational parameters.

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